

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Introduction

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater.

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

(WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

(Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT).

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thaurea* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

nitrite cycle.

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Materials and Methods

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
 - 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
 - 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;
-
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

acidogenic fermentation;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
 - 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
 - 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;
-
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the short-cut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;
- 4°step: Selection of PHA-storing bacteria in Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) via feast-

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

famine selective pressure under aerobic and anoxic conditions for nitrite denitrification;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

- 5°step: PHAs accumulation up to the maximum production capacity.

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

The whole system is represented in Figure 1.1:

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Figure 1 Flowchart of the integrated SCEPHAR system for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant (red line)

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

The Selection SBR had a working volume of 28 L and was inoculated with activated sludge

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

taken from the WWTP of Carbonera (Treviso, North of Italy). The SBR operated according with

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

the operating conditions reported in table 1.1.

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Table 1.1 Operating conditions of the selection SBR during the experimental period

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Parameter	Period 1 (0-39)	Period 2.1 (40-	Period 2.2 (107-145	Previous study
-----------	-----------------	-----------------	---------------------	----------------

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

source

synthetic acetic

synthetic acetic

primary sludge

cellulosic primary

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Electron acceptor

Nitrite

Nitrite

Nitrite

Nitrite

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

vNLR (kgN/m³)

0,61

0,48 ± 0,19

0,56 ± 0,02

0.50 ± 0.11

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Brece Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

tOLR(gCOD/m³d)

1.32±0.12

1.32±0.12

1.18 ± 0,32

1.39 ± 0.11

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

F/M (gCOD-

1,16 ± 0,25

0,67 ± 0,19

0,63 ± 0,09

0,37 ± 0,07

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

SRT (d)

5

7-10

7-10

12 ± 3

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH)

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

In each experimental periods, sample of biomass was taken from the reactor and analysed

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

with Fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH) technique (Amann et al., 1995) coupled with

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

confocal microscopy was used to quantify the biomass distribution. The inoculum of the

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

selection SBR was also examined. Hybridizations were performed with Cy3-labelled specific

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

probes and Cy5-labelled DAPI for most bacteria (Daims et al., 1999). THAU646 were identified

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

as denitrifiers microorganisms that could be involved in PHA accumulation using nitrite as

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

electron acceptor (Neef et al., 1996; Hess et al., 1997; Lajoie et al., 2000). The statistical

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

analysis has been carried out following the method described in Jubany et al. (2009). Here,

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

ImageJ was used as an open source method for quantification of FISH signals. This

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

quantification method is based on analyzing the 40 fields of view as if they were parts of a

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

unique field of view

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Results and discussion

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Selection of PHA storing biomass

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Figure 2(a) shows the long term period of the selection SBR. In period 1 (0-40), losses of

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

floating biomass were frequently observed during the discharge phases: indeed, the biomass

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

raised due to the uncontrolled denitrification and abundant N₂ gas production during the settling

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

phase. Actually, the combination of residual PHA stored ($F/M = 1.2 \text{ gCOD/gMLVSS}$) in the

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

biomass cells and incomplete denitrification favoured conditions for the denitrifying organisms.

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

The latter affected also the degree of PHA biomass selection as it was confirmed by the

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

feast/famine ratio, which never dropped below 0.38 min/min (Figure 2b). In period 2 (46-107),

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

the higher SRT (7-10 days) led to an increase of biomass concentration in the reactor up to

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

around 2.5 gMLVSS/L (data not shown) which boosted the nitrite removal (up to around 92%)

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

and the PHA degradation efficiencies during the famine conditions. From days 40, the $Y_{PHA/VFA}$

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

increased gradually during Period 2, specifically from 0.22 to 0.65 gCOD_{PHA}/gCOD_{VFA}. (Figure

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

1.2). On the other hand, the registered feast/famine ratio was 0.09 (Figure 1.3) at the end of

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

the period 2.2, which indicated high selectivity of the PHA storing biomass.

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Figure 1.2 Profiles of the VFA uptake rate and yield $Y_{PHA/VFA}$ during the experimental period

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Figure 1.3 Long term profile of the feast/famine ratio

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Link between process performance characteristics and microbial population

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

During the experiments, the presence of *Thauera* were analysed through FISH

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

analyses and then linked with the operating performances of the selection SBR. It can

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

be observed from Figure 1.3 that the presence of *Thauera* increased when the system

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

showed the higher stability at SRT of 7-10 days (Period 2.1 and 2.2).

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Figure 1.4 Correlation between the presence of *Thauera* and the operating conditions of the selection SBR (this

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thauera*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Moreover, it seems that the presence of *Thauera* is stable for SRT in the range

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

between 7-15 days. The latter was very clear if the results are compared with previous

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

data reported by Tayà et al., 2016 (paper in preparation). On the other hand, the

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

increase of the $Y_{PHA/VFA}$ from 0.42 to 0.64 gCOD/gCOD could be attributed by the

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

presence of other type of organisms such *Paracoccus* and *Azoarcus*. As reported by

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Albuquerque et al., 2013, *Paracoccus* was shown to take up propionate and valerate

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

more strongly than *Thauera* or *Azoarcus* in a mixed community, thus probably being

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

primarily responsible for the consumption of these VFA.

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Conclusions

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

This study investigated the link between the microbial structure and the performance

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

parameter obtained during the selection of PHA storing biomass via-nitrite using

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

cellulosic sewage sludge as carbon source. The SRT between 7-10 days seems the

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

optimal to achieve high yield of PHA storage (up to 0.65 gCOD_{PHA}/gCOD_{VFA}) as well

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

as to perform high efficiencies of nitrogen removal via-nitrite (up to around 92%) in the

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

selection SBR. The microbial community profile showed that the high presence of

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Thauera at SRT between 7-10 days were comparable with previous findings conducted

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

at SRT of 15 days. Moreover, further investigations should be carry out in order to

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

correlate the increase of PHA storage yield with the presence of other type of bacteria

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

(e.g. *Paracoccus*) performing better the PHA storage than *Thauera*.

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

References

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

of polyhydroxyalkanoates in open, mixed cultures from a waste sludge stream containing high levels

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitrification driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;

between microbial composition and carbon substrate-uptake preferences in a PHA-storing

Linking the process performances of PHA storing biomass selection via-nitrite with the microbial community

N. Frison*, A. Botturi*, E. Righetti*, M. Andreolli*, F. Fatone**

*Department of Biotechnology, Strada Le Grazie, 15, 37134, Verona (Italy)

**Department of Environmental Engineering (SIMAU), via Breccie Bianche, 60131, Ancona (Italy)

Polyhydroxyalkanoates; Volatile Fatty Acids; Anaerobic digestion;

Introduction

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable polymers that can be produced by many different types of bacteria. Activated sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a well-known source of PHA-storing organisms that store these polymers as carbon and energy reserve for biomass growth. PHA production from mixed cultures are accomplished by a sequence of operations which are the following: (i) acidogenic fermentation to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs) from biodegradable organics; (ii) selection of PHA storing biomass in a sequencing batch reactor (SBR); and (iii) a batch process to maximize the PHA accumulation in the bacteria. The selection processes are aerobic and thus are energy intensive; it is estimated that approximately 39 MJ are needed to produce 1 kg of PHA when the a complete aerobic selection is accomplished. The integration of nutrient removal in wastewater treatment systems with the PHA production cycle is currently a challenge. In this work, the PHA storing biomass selection was integrated with the biological nitrogen removal via nitrite process for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant by the use of sieved cellulosic sludge from the wastewater. The novel approach is based on the selection of PHA storing biomass in a Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) by the alternation of aerobic feast conditions for ammonia conversion to nitrite followed by anoxic famine conditions for denitritation driven by internally stored PHA as carbon source. On the other hand, bioplastics as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are formed by wide range of bacteria, which are part of the variety that exists in the wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Recent studies show *Thauera* have often been implicated on PHA production (Dionisi et al., 2006; Albuquerque et al., 2013). Nevertheless, it remains unknown the operational conditions that favour the growth of these organisms.

In this work, the selection degree of PHA storing biomass was evaluated in terms of VFAs uptake rate and yield of PHA production at 5 and 10 days of sludge retention time (SRT). Moreover, FISH analyses were carried out in order to link the operating conditions of the selection SBR with the presence of *Thaurea*, which are involved in the nitrogen removal via-nitrite cycle.

Materials and Methods

The Short-Cut Enhanced PHA Recovery (SCEPHAR)

The SCEPHAR process could be summarized into five main steps:

- 1°step: Sieving of the wastewater to recover cellulosic primary sludge;
- 2°step: Volatile fatty acids (VFAs) production from cellulosic primary sludge by acidogenic fermentation;
- 3°step: Oxidation of ammonia to nitrite in a nitrification reactor via the shortcut pathway;